

RAISING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS' AWARENESS OF THE USE OF EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES TO GET ENGLISH LEARNERS WRITING A GOOD PARAGRAPH: CASE STUDY TEACHER TRAINING SCHOOL-MAGISTÉRIO BG 4011-CUBAL, BENGUELA.

CONSCIENTIZAR OS PROFESSORES DE LÍNGUA INGLESA SOBRE O USO DE ESTRATÉGIAS EFICAZES PARA FAZER COM QUE OS ESTUDANTES DE INGLES ESCREVER UM BOM PARÁGRAFO: ESTÚDIO DE CASO EN UNA ESCUELA DE FORMACIÓN DE DOCENTES-MAGISTERIO BG 4011- CUBAL BENGUELA

SENSIBILIZAR A LOS PROFESORES DE INGLÉS SOBRE EL USO DE ESTRATEIAS EFECTIVAS PARA LOGRAR QUE LOS ESTUDIANTES DE INGLÉS ESCRIBAN UN BUEN PÁRRAFO: ESTÚDIO DE CASO EN UNA ESCUELA DE FORMACIÓN DE DOCENTES-MAGISTERIO BG 4011- CUBAL BENGUELA

SENSIBILISER LES PROFESSEURS D'ANGLAIS À L'UTILISATION DE STRATÉGIES EFFICACES POUR AMENER LES APRENANTS D'ANGLAIS À RÉDIGER UN BOM PARAGRAPHE : ETUDE DE CAS ÉCOLE DE FORMATION DES ENSEIGNANTS-MAGISTÉRIO BG 4011-CUBAL, BENGUELA.

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ABSTRACT

Writing is one of the demanding activity that an instructor should, first and foremost, promote in some of their classes. Being capable of stringing a cluster of words to form a phrase, some phrases to form a sentence, and then sentences to culminate with an effective paragraph, is being quite challenging to some language learners, mainly when the issue lies in writing some scholarly information. Therefore, a great number of ELT secondary school learners have some difficulties to write a correct paragraph. In this sense, writing a correct paragraph requires the mastery of many linguistic sub-

skills. So in building this article, the main and sub-objectives center on raising trainers' awareness and interest to devote more time to the writing teaching; and secondly, using of effective strategies to enable ELT learners writing a good paragraph. The study's general field (topic) is writing. In terms of methodology, three methods were essential for obtaining confident results: questionnaire, observation and text analysis. A correct paragraph should have organization, coherence, cohesion and entirely unified. Consequently, writing accurately a simple letter, an academic essay, a thesis or a dissertation is very complex task if the writer does not have an effective training on paragraph writing. This article is an introductory attempt to help the trainers to improve their learners' art of paragraph writing. This current study came to conclusion that with the application of logical strategies namely **coherence, cohesion, unity, format** and **organization** in writing lessons, the learners could produce an effective paragraph.

Keywords: Writing ; Paragraph; Strategies of teaching English writing.

RESUMO

A escrita de um parágrafo é uma actividade que os professores são obrigados a lidar em algumas das suas aulas. Escrever um bom parágrafo não é tão fácil como o imaginamos, porque um parágrafo é um grupo de frases que desenvolve um único tópico ou uma ideia. No presente texto, propusemo-nos a analisar as diferentes partes do parágrafo, a fim de propor algumas estratégias que possam ajudar os professores dos formandos a lidarem adequadamente com a escrita de parágrafos durante as suas actividades educacional. Metodologicamente, tratou-se de um estudo descritivo, assente no paradigma quali-quantitativo, com recurso aos métodos de pesquisa bibliográfica, observação, análise de textos e o indutivo-dedutivo, tendo os dados sido recolhidos por meio de um inquérito por questionário e entrevista. É o ideal que todos organizem, em qualquer língua, um parágrafo de forma coerente, coesa e unida. O estudo conclui que a aplicação das estratégias lógicas como coerência, coesão, unidade, formatação e estrutura nas aulas escritas poderá efectivamente ajudar os estudantes a escrever um bom paragrafo.

Palavras-chave: Escrita; Parágrafo; Estratégias de Ensino da Escrita em Inglês.

RESUMEN

Un párrafo la escritura s una actividad exigent que los profesores deben afrontar en algunas de seus clases. Escribir un párrafo de corrección requiere el dominio de muchas subhabilidades lingüísticas por parte del escritor. Un párrafo es un grupo de oraciones organizadas logicamente que transmiten una idea precisa. El propósito de esta investigación es discutir las estrategias organizacionales para escribir un párrafo correcto. Este propósito es proponer algunas estrategias de escritura que puedan ayudar a los estudiantes a abordar adecuadamente el proceso de escritura de párrafos durante sus clases de Inglés como lengua extranjera. El campo (tema) general del estudio es la escritura. En terminus de metodología, tres métodos fueron esenciales para obtener resultados confiables: cuestionario, observación y análisis de texto. Um párrafo correcto debe estar organizado en un lenguaje coherente, cohesivo y unificado. En consecuencia, escribir com precisión una carta simpe, un ensayo académico, un trabajo o una disertación es una tarea muy compleja si el escritor tiene una formción eficaz en la redacción de párrafos. Es decir, este artículo es un intento introductorio para ayudar a los formadores mejorar su El art de los estudiantes de escribir párrafos. El estudio actual concluye que com la aplicación de estrategias lógicas a saber , coherencia, cohesión, unidad, formato y organización en las lecciones de escritura, los alumnos podrían producir un párrafo eficaz.

Palabras clave: Redacción; Párrafo; Estrategias de Enseñanza de la Escritura Inglesa.

RÉSUMÉ

Un paragraphe l'écriture est une activité exigeante que les instructeurs divent aborder dans certains de leurs cours. La redaction d'un paragraphe correct necessite la maîtrise de nombreuses sous-compétences linguistiques chez l'écrivain. Un paragraphe est un groupe de phrases logiquement organisées qui véhiculent une idée precise. Le but de cette recherche est de discuter dès stratégies organisationnelles pour rédiger un paragraphe correct. Cet objectif est de proposer quelques strategies d'écriture qui peuvent aider les apprenants `a gérer correctement le processus d'écriture de paragraphes pendant leurs cours d'anglais langue étrangère. Le domaine général (sujet) de l'étude est l'écriture. En termes de méthodologie, trois methods se sont avérées essentielles pour obtenir des résultats fiables: le questionnaire, l'observation et l'anlyse de texte. Un paragraphe correct doit être organisé dans un langage cohérent, cohésive et

unifié. Par conséquent, rédiger avec précision une simple lettre, un essai académique ou un mémoire est une tâche très complexe si l'écrivain dispose d'une formation efficace en rédaction de paragraphes. C'est-à-dire que cet article est une tentative d'introduction pour aider les formateurs à améliorer leur l'art de l'écriture de paragraphes par les apprenants. La présente étude conclut qu'avec l'application de stratégies logiques, à savoir la cohérence, la cohésion, l'unité, le format et l'organisation dans les cours d'écriture, les apprenants pourraient produire un paragraphes efficace

Mots-clés: Rédaction; Paragraphe; Stratégies d'Enseignement de l'Écriture Anglaise.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current work is going to portray two angles of writing namely, (i) writing in general sense, in which two sub-headings will be the focuses, such as, the nature of writing skills and process writing. And the second is (ii) writing a paragraph in particular, in this section, three sub-headings will be the pivots namely, paragraph types, paragraph writing strategies such as, cohesion, coherence, unity, format and organization and how to write a good paragraph.

In general term, writing is a cognitive activity performed by someone who is totally resourced by effective strategies and principles of writing. In fact, Wilson (2022) assures that writing is way of externalizing all input stored in a human's mind down on a physical or digital format. In this light of thought, Richards and Schmidt (2010) advocate that writing is a complex cognitive task that makes the writer to devote their entire knowledge and systematize every single step in phases of planning, drafting, revising and editing. It alerts us that conducting any effective writing activity implies from a writer, first and foremost, learning how to conceptualise, formulate, and then put the thoughts and/or the ideas down on a sheet of paper or electronic device. This process becomes more and more challenging when the issue does not only center on writing itself, but also how to write a paragraph accordingly.

Regarding another side of the coin, in broad sense, a paragraph is a cluster of logical sentences whose primary goal is to convey a piece of meaningful information. In this perspective, Johnson (2012) depicts that 'a paragraph represents a unit of thought, and the fact that the sentences within the paragraph all relate to the same topic give it unity and coherence' (84). As matter of fact, lacking of such effective paragraph writing strategies such as, cohesion, coherence unity, format and organization in writing

activity, make a great number of ELT secondary school learners undergo some extreme difficulties to write a correct paragraph.

To scrutinize data collected from a chosen setting (Cubal-Benguela-Angola), and also give validity as well as reliability to a group of instructors and learners who belong to the teaching of English as a foreign Language, we formulated the following question:

- *What can be done to help grade 11 ELT learners in “Magistério Cubal” to write a well-structured paragraph?*

After raising the first question we have moved to the reformulation of another one:

- *Which writing principles should be considered when organizing a well-structured paragraph?*

It is generally known that writing a good paragraph involves some knowledge of branches of linguistics such as composition, grammar, morphology, syntax, and so on. This fact makes paragraph writing a very complex activity. Also, to apply writing principles when we organize a well-structured paragraph. In this respect, this work is really meant to raise trainers’ awareness and interest to devote more time to the writing teaching; and secondly, using effective strategies to enable ELT learners writing a good paragraph.

As the primary goals is to cover some gaps found in the previous researches, through our investigations, we found in ‘Instituto Superior de Ciências da Educação- ISCED in Benguela’s library’ a research work which focused on writing in general but not on writing a coherent paragraph, see:

- Tchindumbulu (2013). A suggestion of Activities to Improve Writing Skills to Grade 12 Juridical Economic Students at Secondary School in Benguela. And
- Sanumala (2013). A suggestion of some Activities for Developing Writing Skills in Grade 8 at Rei Katyavala Secndary School in Lobito.

The research works mentioned above are different from ours in many remarkable aspects and the most important are:

- The setting of the work above was different from ours;
- The focus is different from ours;
- We use text analysis, which was not used by the former researchers.

So we must assure that this work is truly more integral than those aforesaid, due to the sorts of methodology used, the number of paragraph writing strategies adopted namely, coherence, cohesion, unity, format and organization.

2. WRITING

Writing is an activity that implies turning an intangible thing (idea or thought) into tangible one. It is a skill apart from speaking which makes a learner produces linguistic items to create a meaningful excerpt. Thus, it demands a writer to conceptualize and formulate accordingly the output before exteriorizing it down on a sheet of paper and/or other forum of writing in order to avoid ambiguity or misunderstanding to the reader or listener. In this view, Prichard (2013) says that by starting and ameliorating writing ability, learners can develop effective scholarly practices for drafting and composing task. Yet, learners' writing in this public setting may feel their text has greater authenticity and purpose in comparison to traditional writing which may only be viewed by an instructor.

The accounts above teaches us that writing is a subject that is very important for any academic stakeholder mainly for students. Students can increase their ability through writing subject. In writing teaching and learning process, student will be guided by a lecturer. Firstly, the lecturer will explain the theory of writing, and then students apply the material in real activity. They will try to write about one topic and they should write a composition based on topic which is given by the lecturer. Then the lecturer will give some exercises for the students to write about some topics and from the result the lecturer will know whether the students have understood the material or not. Therefore, students should pay attention to writing subject. The students are hoped to be able to write a good product and they also can increase their knowledge in writing.

Writing carries multiple-functions. We use writing to perform different social task such as, communicating with others through written message, conveying the meaning, and informing some issues concerning current, previous or future situation and entertaining with pal friends: pen pal, key pal or mouse pal through internet, Facebook, WhatsApp, e-mail. Furthermore, educational practitioners such as, learners and teachers interact each other in the classroom via written task. Researchers find out certain data by using writing, politicians influence population to vote for or against with a piece of written advertisement, police regulate the traffic network through writing and record as well as

solve some issues relating a certain society through writing. Therefore, writing activity is the key point to take into consideration through entire social activity, mostly in academic life. In this respect,

2.1 The Nature of Writing Skills

Writing is highly seen as a thing that involving a process that is applied repeatedly and complex activity to deal within the classroom or outdoor. In this respect, in EFL classrooms, writing skills can develop rapidly students' abilities to think, to compose and to organize when they are given numerous opportunities to write. Most of writing activities are done to fulfil some well-known learning objectives, such as to facilitate the use of some expressions, to consolidate the learning of grammar or to teach new vocabulary, to think and to produce ideas on a matter.

Writing has some aspects in common with other skills, but it also differs to them in some significant ways. Therefore, many methodologists have currently spent more time in developing writing materials to help teachers cope with students' inabilities to write especially in foreign language.

Concerning the 'nature of writing skills', there are many opinions regarding this issue. Richards and Schmidt (2010) say that "writing is viewed as the result of complex processes of planning, drafting, reviewing and revising" (p.p. 640,641). This means that to be able to write a good paragraph or an essay, people should go through many stages like prewriting, composing / writing, rewriting / revision and master many subskills. In fact, writing is a complex process which involves series of abilities and sub-skills such as handwriting or typing, spelling, punctuations, sentences and paragraphs construction, organisation of ideas, etc. As a result, in EFL classrooms, writing skills can develop rapidly students' abilities to think, to compose and to organize when they are given numerous opportunities to write. Most of writing activities are done to fulfil some well-known learning objectives, such as to facilitate the use of some expressions, to consolidate the learning of grammar or to teach new vocabulary, to think and to produce ideas on a matter. Writing, just like reading, is in many ways a solitary activity which is performed individually.

2.2 Process Writing or Writing Process

The term process writing or writing process is widely used in English as a second Language or English as a foreign Language (ESL or EFL) classrooms. And it is

worthier than a simple writing process approach to teaching writing. As the expression ‘process’ suggests, it has to do with systems of writing by going on from one point, that is pre-writing, to the next drafting, revising and so on. Wilson (2022) accounts for process writing as follows:

“ Writing is best done in a sequence. Each step sets you up to take the next step. If you find that something isn’t clicking in your paper, it’s often because you tried to skip over or move too quickly through one of the steps,” (16).

Consequently, Johnson (2012) contends that ‘the important thing is to recognize that good writing simply cannot be produced in one attempt’ (100). So it teaches us that a paragraph is a process-oriented writing in four general steps or stages: prewriting or invention, drafting, revising, and editing. In here, writing is entirely set apart from the written product; and it simply leads learners through various stages of writing process. Moreover, in this complex field of writing process, ‘ the most important factor to be obeyed is the first stage (prewriting), and the coming ones can be chosen at random order, i.e., the process can go on revising, drafting and then culminating in editing. Surely, it is imperative that the learners have to understand that the stages are not fixed. So, in this sense, it teaches us that when the writing lesson takes place, the first point to take into account whenever initiating writing is prewriting stage due to its features such as, the creation of topic to be discussed, the gathering of ideas and/or thoughts and then the organization of the ideas and/or thoughts. Learners can start drafting their writing before going through revision or revising before drafting and vice-versa it will not affect the entire writing.

Pre-writing- is the first stage of the writing process. It is the foundation of a successful paragraph. As was accounted before without the prewriting stage, nothing can be drafted, revised and edited. During this stage we are thinking about the topic, brainstorming, focusing, and developing a working thesis. Therefore, Mogahed (2013) asserts that during this phase several prewriting strategies are used to help the writer to generate, contextualize, organize, and focus ideas on the topic.

Drafting – if we obey the rule we must say that draft comes after the prewriting. In this phase the writing process can take up quite a bit of time, and includes other elements of the writing process such as collecting the materials and the ideas. It is important to

remember that the goal of the drafting stage is to take your outline and to develop a paper for the materials and ideas collection. The writer should focus on the content and make sure that the ideas are clear and well detailed. A draft can be written several times till we get a final version of the work. As a matter of fact, Dziak (2018) distinguishes two main types of drafts: **rough drafts and final drafts**. Rough drafts are the first segment of the drafting process, where someone is placing information on the page. A rough draft may undergo editing by the writer, but it is not the polished version of the assignment (hence the reason why it is ‘rough’). While, **final drafts** have been edited numerous times by the author, and may also undergo the benefit of correction by a proof-reader’ (p.3). So it teaches us that the final draft is regarded as a the be-all and end-all process in writing process because several error corrections were already made.

Revising - Looking at the parts of the word *revise*: The prefix *re-* means *again* or *a new*, and *-vise* comes from the same root as *vision* that is to see. Thus, revising is «**re-seeing**» the composition in a new way. That is why revising refers to improving the **global** structure and content of your paper, its **organization and ideas**, not grammar, spelling, and punctuation. In this sense, M.Pd (2019) says that “revising is the way that a piece of writing is seen and analysed in order to change some points that cannot fit as such through the entire writing. Honestly, it educates us that during the revising stage, the writer should read the writing and look at the content. The writer can think of revising as looking at the big picture. Yet, in this stage of writing process, the language learner does not need yet to worry about the mechanics of the handwriting, spelling, punctuation, etc.), but focus on the content. Before starting the revising and editing stages, it is important to set the right environment, that is, appropriate setting for a successful writing. In fact, And the last not least in this process is editing.

Editing- is the last stage of writing process, obviously if the intention is to follow the order . It is about looking at mistakes and errors encountered in the text and correcting them. It is important to take enough time with this stage. Nordquist (2019) emphasizes that during this stage, the editor tries very hard to achieve saturation point by improving paragraph or essay by making all the linguistic features through a paragraph fit together in order to make sense. Just to assure to go through this process implies reordering, omitting, deleting and adding some words or phrases.

Considering all the points mentioned previously, we might say that writing in English is a multidimensional, complex, and difficult process. It is conscious language skill that should be mastered by the writer. Plus, writing involves word-level skills, cognitive abilities, and sub-skills. There are many skills and sub-skills involved in writing, and there is no doubt that good writing skills usually develop from extensive reading, some specific training, and a good deal of practice. To some extent, good writing skills require to learner developing the following basic skills: handwriting or typing, spelling, constructing appropriate grammatical sentences, punctuating, organizing the ideas into a logical sequence, structuring the sequence, editing the draft and writing the final text.

After dealing with writing in general, we are already on occasion to look at paragraph , plus its two sub-headings. A paragraph is a well-organized set of sentences that describes a topic or an idea. Each sentence in a paragraph must give information about the topic. Also, the sentences must be in the right order so that every reader can understand and appreciate the piece of information it comprises.

3 PARAGRAPH

In order to reach a saturation point of a good paragraph formation, a language learner needs, first and foremost, to go through some steps for instances, morphemes to form a word, words to form a clause and clauses to form a sentence. Therefore, a paragraph is a combination of sentences in which all sentences relate to one main thought in order to convey an accurate meaning. According to Sheehy and Wray (2019) paragraph is series of sentences that all the sentences focus only on one main proposal. Additionally, Yule (2014) underscores that a paragraph is a form of written communication which contains a minimum of five sentences. Each sentence in a paragraph ‘talks about’ or develops one single main idea. If a paragraph does this, it is said to have unity. So each sentence in a paragraph must be tied up to the one before and after it, like links in a chain, by using special words called transitions. If your paragraph contains these links, it is said to have coherence. On the other hand, a paragraph can also be comprised by only one sentence in case the core issue does not concern formality (formal), i.e., not academic writing but creative or personal writing. If the academic issue is a pivot, then the paragraph should be comprised by more than one sentence. So in this sense, we may say that number of sentences is not determined conventionally; it depends really

upon the type of paragraph and the idea developed in it. A paragraph should be long enough to develop the main idea clearly, however.

3.1 Paragraph Types

According to Kemper, et. al (2016) there are four main types of paragraphs. For describing something, write a descriptive paragraph. For telling a story, write a narrative paragraph. For explaining something, write an explanatory paragraph and for expressing your opinion, write a persuasive (argument) paragraph. In this light of sense, it teaches us that a teacher before getting his or her learners acquainted with paragraph strategies, he or she should primarily provide a brief account of paragraph taxonomy in order to systemize well the teaching and learning process of an effective paragraph.

3.2 Paragraph writing Strategies

The coherence, cohesion, unity, format and organisation are the main characteristics of a good paragraph writing. These characteristics facilitate the understanding of the paragraph by the readers. As a matter of fact, these five elements are entirely regarded as the effective strategies that a writing learner has to consider when writing a paragraph. So the first one to account for is the organization.

Organisation- the English writing organization style is quite simple, which has a beginning, middle and an end. In fact, the beginning should say that what the article is going to be about, the middle should talk about the topic of the article, and the end should say what the article was about. As a matter of fact, a paragraph is the basic unit of academic or other types of writing (creative, institutional, personal) in English; therefore, students who want to be a writer, or even study at university need to learn how to write a paragraph because all other types of academic writing such as essays, reports, compositions, and research papers are based on it. An academic paragraph has a very specific organizational pattern. When we follow this pattern, the paragraph will be easy for the readers to understand. This simple pattern is based on topic sentence, supporting sentences and concluding sentence.

With a great regard to organization we must say that a paragraph should be made up of three kinds of sentences or more which explain the main idea, opinion or feeling about the subject. A paragraph should have: topic sentence, supporting sentences, and

concluding sentence. However, some authors whose philosophies are pretty much centered on four types of sentences, which is, the fourth one lies in writer's comment.

Kemper, Rathan, and Sebrank (2016) explain that the topic sentence is the most general statement of the paragraph. It is the key sentence because it names the subject and the controlling idea: the writer's main idea, opinion, or feeling about that topic. The topic sentence can come at the beginning or at the end of a paragraph. You should write your topic sentence as the first sentence of your paragraph for two reasons: first, it will tell the reader what he or she is going to say; second, the reader can look back at the topic sentence often as he or she writes the supporting sentences. It will help the reader stay on the subject as he or she writes.

The quotations above clue us on that the starting sentence explains the main idea of the paragraph, and it provides us a clue of starting to develop main body of the paragraph. Apart from topic sentence, a paragraph is comprised also by supporting ones which are the sentences that meant to assist the first one by providing some examples, details, statistics and so on. On the same wavelength, Johnson (2012) stresses that the supporting sentences follow the first one and also play a critical role of sustaining and developing the entire paragraph. And the last sentences is called conclusion which presents the substance in a concluding way.

In terms of the last point of paragraphing, writing a concluding sentence or summing up a sentence which tells the reader that the paragraph is finished and the paragraph development has ended. Regarding conclusion concept, Sheehy and Wray (2019) portrays that conclusion lies in gathering all the points mentioned in previous sentences (topic sentence or supporting ones) but in brief way and by using different expressions.

All in all, the topic sentence is most of the times the starting sentence because it gives the reader an idea of what he or she is going to read, whereas the concluding sentence finishes the paragraph. Therefore, the topic sentence can help the reader or listener to focus on key point of the concerned paragraph. Relating to supporting statements, the simplest way is to rephrase the topic sentence asking a question of how it can be proved.

After giving some account on paragraph organization, it is time to look at coherence.

Coherence: means that each point should be linked to the previous and following points to help the paragraph flow and progress logically and clearly. An easy way to link

paragraph's features together is through transitions in each topic sentence of paragraph. As a result, John (2013) says coherence is concerned with the overall interpretation of a text as a unified piece of discourse, not just the formal links.

Generally, we consider a certain paragraph has coherence if it is comprised by a series of sentences which convey a good writing like, topic sentence, supporting sentences and concluding sentence that develop a main idea at once. And within these three sentences, some aspects should be distinctly emphasised such as: chronological order - which has to do with organization of the sentences in a paragraph. i.e., the first sentence that should appear in the paragraph, the second and the next etc. etc. clarity of the use of nouns instead of personal pronouns-which helps a reader to understand well the text and avoid ambiguity and misunderstanding. The use of transitional words and phrases- for showing a good relationship between clause and sentence.

Cohesion: when a paragraph has cohesion all the supporting sentences connect to each other in their support of the topic sentence. Cohesion consists on having a text being contextually well connected. That is to say, every subsequent linguistic feature such as, reference, substitution, ellipsis, transition, repetition, synonym, superordinate and general word, in a paragraph should cohere with every previous item in a paragraph either exophorically or endophorically (anaphora or cataphora) to make a message have sense.

With a high consideration of all linguistic features afore-commented, we decided to give a slight detail about transitional devices that from our understanding seem to be a bit more complex feature to deal with in a paragraph writing. Below are some accounts:

transitional device is a grammatical technique which connects two different parts having the same identity; in the present case, two clauses and/or sentences. Also, transitional device allows us to flow smoothly from one paragraph to the next by joining the ideas of both paragraphs. In addition, transitional words or phrases help unite disparate paragraphs to generate a unified theme. Moreover, Helen (2019) cited in M.Pd (2019) portrays that “transitional words and phrases can create powerful links between ideas in your paper and can help your reader understand the logic of your paper. However these words all have different meanings, nuances, and connotations.” Furthermore, Lili (2021) states that transitional devices are words or phrases that connect all the entire linguistic features through a text without losing the logical part of the it. Surely, it

teaches us that readers will be able to trace a writer's ideas and comprehend how they relate to one another if the writer uses phrases like 'in addition' or 'moreover', which will make for a smoother, more enjoyable reading experience. This is especially important for essayists and bloggers, who frequently share a single concept with their audience at a time.

Unity: is the continuity of a single idea (the thesis) throughout the essay. Each detail and example should develop logically and refer back to the original focus. Coherence means that each point should be linked to the previous and following points to help the paragraph flow and progress logically and clearly. An easy way to link paragraphs together is through transitions in each paragraph's topic sentence. When all the supporting sentences are related to the topic sentence; in this sense, we might say that the paragraph has unity. John (2013) delineates that the objective and the concept of a paragraph, both center on one topic and on one fundamental point. It conveys a logical idea and the fact that all sentences within the paragraph are truly connected in the same topic and the sentences give it unity and coherence.

Format: by building an effective framework of a certain project, it always demands from the builder to obey and subsequently follows some basic parameters such as, the length, width, height... of the terrain so that when the project has erected every single part of the building will cohere with one another. Obviously, this kind of demand is attained through all field of knowledge, and the composition of a paragraph is not an exception. In English language, it is compulsory to know the format of paragraph if the intention is to write correctly. Therefore, every academic work, mostly written one should be well-formatted in order to avoid a misunderstanding or interpretation to the reader or listener.

To delineate on where a paragraph should begin and end: in sense of left line as well as right line from margins, also on the top side and bottom side of the page, also the first sentence on the paper, and then a word, a phrase and a sentence writing in linear style (straight-line), a writer has to establish choices of some methods. First of all, the writer has to delimit the organisation of the margin of the page to be written down on; secondly, the writer has to start writing the first sentence on the paper by giving some spaces, and then he or she has to put the writing on straight line. On the same thought of line, Wilson (2022) depicts that "having a good idea is not the same having a good paper: an idea is an interpretation, a paper an articulation. Don't allow your good ideas

to be murdered by bad papers''(184). It teaches us that apart from teaching our learners about how to connect linguistic features in the entire text, it is also imperative that physical part of the writing should be emphasised in the lesson.

Regarding two sorts of forum of writing (paper and digital), the physical one seems to be a bit more complex. Writing a paragraph down on a sheet of paper with no lines, makes the process of writing more difficult to get a writer's handwriting through straight line. A writer without writing skills linear, his or her sentence almost always tends to slope backward and/or forward. Unlike unlined paper, lined paper exerts a huge role in the process of producing straight-lined handwriting. Therefore, lined paper consists on having lines printed or drawn across the paper. When the question is writing a paragraph by hand, surely, lined paper helps the writer to build a legible and a neat handwriting.

There are certain numbers of rules which have to be followed while writing a standard paragraph from the point of view of format. Formatting a paragraph in writing is not only devoted to what extent to previous points highlighted, but also on handwriting skills. So far as we are concerned, paragraph writing can be conducted through three forums: writing a paragraph using 'computer' (typed paragraph); writing a paragraph using 'typewriter' (typewritten paragraph) or writing a paragraph by 'hand' (handwritten paragraph).

In fact, the three forums should be taken into account whenever dealing with paragraph writing. Obviously, apart from formats of a paragraph which were already highlighted before, irrespective of writing a paragraph using typewriter and writing a paragraph using computer, we think that the chief point this process is legibility and neatness in writing.

3.3 How to write a good paragraph

There are many different ways to develop a paragraph. Knowing what they are and how to use them can help you better convey what you need to in certain parts of your essay. Here is an example of how to write a paragraph based on our own insights:

The persuasive paragraph

A man who wanted to study Portuguese at ISCED

My friend Pereira is very good at speaking Portuguese; being so, he decided to apply for a Portuguese course at ISCED Benguela. When we were together at my house, he told me about his wishes. So, I told him that Portuguese is our official language and almost everybody can speak it, and I advise him to rather try to apply for an English course. I said: Why don't you try English? I know that you are good in it and you will be a professional polyglot and then many companies will be looking for you to work for them and you will be respected by many people. So, he agreed and made it at ISCED and he was very happy and successful.

The above paragraph is well-written because the words cohere with one another, the sentences are unified and also the messages are moving smoothly and logically from one point to the next. Concerning organization of the paragraph:

Topic sentence: starts from (My friend ... to ...at ISCED Benguela.)

Supporting sentences: start from (when we were ... to ... by many people).

Concluding sentence: starts from (so he agreed... to ... happy and successful).

4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

The purpose of any research is to find some plausible answers to the research questions set up as guiding principles for conducting a given study research through the application of scientific procedures. That is, research seeks to find out the truth which is hidden and which has been partially or not yet discovered. However, it is important not to forget that each research study has its own specific purpose and its own background in terms of the previous studies done in the specific field area such as the one under study. Just to remind as mentioned previously, this research intends to raise ELT learners's awaness of effective writing strategies to write a good paragraph.

According to (Tavakoli,2012),

Research is a systematic process of collecting and analyzing data that will investigate a research problem or question, or help researchers obtain a more complete understanding of a situation. The goal of research is to describe, explain, or predict present or future phenomena (p. 545).

Looking at the definition above we can tell that research is the need of finding out the truth with the help of study, observation, comparison and/or experiment. In other words, the research seeks the knowledge through objective and systematic methods of finding solutions to a problem.

4.1 Methodology

Methodology has to do with set of methods and procedures used through a scientific work in order to facilitate the collection of data as well as the design of the research work. (Tavakoli, 2012) 's definition, (Richards and Schmidt, 1992, p. 229) posit that *“methodology is the procedure used in carrying out an investigation including the methods used to collect and analyse data.”* This account illustrates the important elements of the methodology used by the investigator when designing research work. These elements are: the population and the respective setting of the research, period of study and research methods.

Data Collection

Collecting data, depends very much on the way the researcher organizes the study. This includes the types of the instruments the researcher is going to use to collect data. For example, the triangulation in this research is based on three types of instruments namely questionnaires, observation and text analysis because we intended to have more time on a observation in a way to see teachers' beliefs on how they teach writing lessons.

As a definition of data, (Tavakoli, 2012) poses that data refers to the information collected in a research study. The author adds that data can be oral and recorded or written, in the forms of essays, test scores, diaries, and so on. This implies that the quality and utility of monitoring, evaluation and research in our projects is related to our ability to collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data. More specifically, the study selects appropriate methodologies to collect data and attempts to understand the difference between quantitative and qualitative data, and associates benefits and limitations. Indeed, data collection looks at an overview of common methods and data analysis techniques for both quantitative and qualitative research and finally discusses the interpretation of findings using multiple data sources.

4.3 Research methods

Research methods are the strategies; processes or techniques utilized in the collection of data or evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create better understanding of a topic. According to the type of study there are different types of research methods which use different tools for data collection. Oxford Word Power Dictionary (2012) defines “a method as being an organized and systematic way to find answers to questions”(p. 465). From this understanding, this research comprises two research methods to respond to the research questions as discussed later. This study consists of a mixed approach type of research with a combination of qualitative and quantitative data. Nevertheless, from all that has been mentioned so far, it can be concluded that data refers to the evidences. They can be both qualitative and quantitative as it is the case in this article. They are collected for both variables as well as attributes which are gathered in terms of frequency and scores, but they depend on the type of instrument employed for measurement.

Yet, from the definitions above, it becomes easy to understand that a method is way of finding truth concerning an existing phenomenon from all or selected number of respondents of the concerned universe. Under this perspective, interview facilitates to get in-depth data on the current practices and challenges.

Nonetheless, this research comprises two methods to give the answer to the question raised as discussed next. Just as mentioned earlier, this research is fundamentally qualitative and quantitative in which one school namely, Magistério GB-4011-Cubal was the setting. In addition, three research tools are selected for gathering data, namely questionnaires and text analysis together with classroom observation. These three research tools were helpful in gathering as much information as possible in order to test the hypotheses mentioned earlier in a way to test the hypothesis in different angles.

It should be emphasized that for the purpose of this study the only way that we found most feasible was to collect data from schools, from teachers and students in their real world not for methodology related issues but to see how much teachers know about effective strategies raise learners' awareness to write a good paragraph.

5 DATA PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Results

This section is about the presentation of the results collected in the field by using different tools, namely a teachers’ questionnaire, a students’ questionnaire, textual analyses and classroom observation charts.

5.1 Results from teachers’ questionnaire

1. What is your academic degree (speciality and degree)?

Table 1: Teachers’ specialisation

Options	TA	TB	TC	TD	TE
Undergraduate in ELT	0	0	0	0	0
Undergraduate in another field	0	0	0	0	0
Graduate in ELT	1	0	1	0	1
Graduate in another Field	0	0	0	1	0
Master in ELT	0	0	0	0	0
Master in another Field	0	1	0	0	0

Source: Our own table.

The outcomes of the questions above are expressed as follows teacher A, C and E are graduated in ELT at ISCED-Benguela, whereas teacher B is a Master in another area, and teacher D is graduated in another field.

2. How long have you been teaching English?

Graph 1: Teaching Experience

Source: our own graph.

The outcomes of the second question addressed to teachers are presented in graphic one as follows: teacher B is the most experienced in the field with 25 years of teaching experience, teacher D is the second most experienced with 14 years, teacher C is the third one with 11 years, the next is teacher A with 6 and last one is teacher E with 5 years.

**3. Have you already taught these strategies used in writing a correct paragraph?
(More than one answer is acceptable)**

Strategies related to paragraph organization: topic sentence; detailed sentence and concluding sentence; _____.

Logical strategies: -sentences connectors and transitional connectors; _____.

Prolific strategies: fluency of ideas. _____.

Strategies related to grammar (constructing good sentences, using correcting phrases)_____.

Table 2: Strategies applied by teachers

	TA	TB	TC	TD	TE
Strategies related to paragraph organization: topic sentence; detailed sentence and concluding sentence	0	0	0	0	0
Logical strategies: sentences connectors and transitional connectors	1	1	0	0	1
Prolific strategies: fluency of ideas	0	1	0	1	1
Strategies related to grammar (constructing good sentences, using correctly phrases)	1	1	1	1	1
	TA	TB	TC	TD	TE
Strategies related to paragraph organization: topic sentence; detailed sentence and concluding sentence	0	0	0	0	0
Logical strategies: sentences connectors and transitional connectors	1	1	0	0	1
Prolific strategies: fluency of ideas	0	1	0	1	1
Strategies related to grammar (constructing good sentences, using correctly phrases)	1	1	1	1	1

Source: Our own table.

As we can see the results in the table above should be read in two senses: vertically and horizontally. In the vertical sense, the results should be read referring to the teacher B and E who have already used more strategies than the others. Teachers A, D and C have used fewer strategies than B and E. In the horizontal sense, we have to refer to each strategy. Strategy b) has been used by 3 teachers (A, B and E), strategy c) has been also used by 3 teachers (B, D

and E); finally, strategy d) is used by all the teachers. Strategy a) has not been used by any teacher.

4. Among the linguistic aspects given below, which one is the most difficult for the learners to learn?

- a) Speaking b) Writing c) Reading d) Listening e) Grammar f) Pronunciation g) Vocabulary

Table 3: The most difficult linguistic aspects for the learners

	TA	TB	TC	TD	TE	Percentage of teachers
Speaking	1	0	0	0	0	20%
Writing	0	1	1	1	0	60%
Reading	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Listening	0	0	0	0	1	20%
Grammar	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Pronunciation	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Vocabulary	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Linguistic aspect						100%

Source: Our own table

These questions were addressed to EFL teachers to know the most difficult aspects they have already explored. According to the outcomes writing is the most difficult with 60% whereas listening and speaking have each 20%.

After having presented the results from teacher questionnaire in graph, diagram, illustrations and tables, we are moving onto the next point to present the results from students' questionnaire.

5.2 Results from students' questionnaire

This subsection is about presentation of the results obtained from students' questionnaire. We are carrying out an investigation on writing a correct paragraph with secondary school grade 11 trainees. From this questionnaire, we intended to collect some necessary pieces of information about writing a correct paragraph in English from secondary school grade 11 trainees in ELT speciality. Participants were kept anonymous.

1. Which grade have you started to learn English?

Diagram1: Students first contact with the English language

Source: Our own diagram.

This question was posed to students to know the grade in which they started to learn English. According to the outcomes most of them started learning English in the grade 7, (55%), whereas grade 8 is the second with 14%, and grade 9 is the third with 12%. In the next position come grade 6 and 5 with 9% and 6% for grade 5, the last one is grade 10 with 6%.

2 Do you have any extra-trainings (an English proficiency centre) apart from the one you have at school?

Diagram 2: students extra-training

Source: Our own diagram.

The last question on the previous page, helps us to know if the students have extra- training after school. According to the outcomes 54 students have never had extra-training whereas 12 students have extra-training after normal school.

3. What language aspect seems very difficult for you? (NB: it is possible to cross more than one options)

Diagram 3: most difficult language aspect for the students

Source: Our own diagram.

This question helps us to know in general the most difficult language aspect from the students which according to the diagram above writing is the most difficult which range on 30%, while speaking is the second with 21%, and on third position comes listening with 15%, the next is reading with 11%; grammar and vocabulary seems to be compulsory to the students with 5% and 6% for vocabulary.

5.3 Results from text analyses

This subsection deals with the analyses made on some paragraphs written by the students. It was designed by students own topic and only four (2) written work, among sixty-six (66) paragraphs, chosen randomly to be analysed.

Below we bring illustrations of such texts which we have analysed them thoroughly. Furthermore, as this fourth chapter focuses only on presentation of results, then, we are discussing and analysing such texts in the later chapter of this article which is the fifth chapter. Being so, we invite you to have a look at the texts illustrated below.

Illustration 1

Dear Teacher

I'm very sorry for not coming to ~~the~~ school yesterday. I didn't come because I drank something bad and had to see ~~at~~ a nurse quickly. I'm afraid Ransen is also going to be away for a long time. In fact we may not see him at school again.

Please give me any work I missed yesterday. I'll make sure I do it.

Illustration 2

Once upon a time!
 a boy that always dreamed in be a teacher, he always
 read big books about the education and wanted (about) one
 day in that he appeared than the school than he wanted
 only allows make inscription as the pupils than are with
 média fourteen (14) and he needed very the média fourteen (14)
 to be his certified the he wanted learn more get more
 notes in fact that he needed then study very much
 for a teacher and he said the year mother: one day
 I'm going to writer some books about me and he did
 many books about himself, and he stayed famous with
 their books.

We have just presented the texts which we are going to analyze in the fifth chapter of this book. And now, once we illustrated the texts we worked with, we are inviting you to come with us to the next section in which we are presenting the results from classroom observation.

5.4 Results from classroom observation chart

This subsection deals with classroom activities which have a strait impact on writing. After observing 5 teachers, each of them once we have noticed some remarkable situation which can be shown up. This qualitative data will help us to have a clear idea on what grade 11 teachers of the school do to improve their students' writing skills. When they were delivering their lesson the following aspects could be noticed by everybody who was devoted to ELT classroom activities: 1: Lesson planning and sequence of activities in a different lesson stages; 2: Classroom management: organization of the classroom in order to create an excellent environment to make students learn; 3: Use activities that improve writing skills and paragraph writing: Checking whether the teacher use activities that enables the students to improve their writing skills; 4: Students involvement in the writing activities: Checking the students' involvement in the classroom activities; 5: Frequency in teaching writing skills: Checking the frequency in which teachers taught writing skills in the classroom; 6: Checklist G: Frequency in exploring activities dealing with paragraph: Checking the frequency in which teachers use paragraph activities in the classroom; and 7: Strategies and technique used by the teacher to improve students writing skills.

Since this article is based on paragraph writing strategies, we failed in observing lesson which is totally destined to writing skills. Most of the lessons observed were focused principally on speaking, reading and some grammar. Unfortunately, the five teachers have never taught the specific strategies and techniques related to a correct paragraph. In this section we are finishing, we have dealt with all aspects concerning the utilised data collection methods. In the next section we are going to analyse and discuss the results presented in this section.

The results of the third question as they are presented in the diagram number 1 show that the options: *a) Basing on a text studied at school* and *b) Basing on the activities explored during English classes* are the most used when choosing the topics of the compositions because each of this option represents 40%; whereas one teacher represents only 20%.

6 DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In this Chapter we are going to analyse and discuss the results presented in previous Chapter. Data analysis is the process of collecting, modelling, and analysing data using various statistical and logical methods and techniques.

6.1 Analysis and Discussion of Results from Teachers' Questionnaire

The first question was posed to 5 EFL teachers to know about their graduations and specialities. It is important to have such knowledge before criticising a teacher's performance in the classroom about a given topic. As we know teachers who were trained in ELT have a good performance in teaching English than any other who was trained in another field.

The second question was addressed to 5 EFL teachers to know about the lasting of their experience in teaching English, as people say, «experience is the best teacher». We believe that those teachers who have a long experience in teaching English have passed through difficult teacher situation to which they attempted to give satisfactory solution. As a matter of fact, teaching writing as considered as difficult situation in ELT because it depends on many skills and sub skills.

The results of the third question as they are presented in the diagram number 1 show that the options: *a) Basing on a text studied at school* and *b) Basing on the activities explored during English classes* are the most used when choosing the topics of the compositions because each of this option represents 40%; whereas one teacher represents only 20%.

The fourth question was addressed to EFL teachers to know the most difficult aspect they have already explored in EFL classes. It is known that writing is the most difficult among all the skills, because it requires some knowledge of grammar, morph-syntax, phraseology, semantic, pragmatics, sentence logics, etc. The result obtained from this question confirms the complexity of writing skills. With English language many people can express themselves well but not being able to write correctly. According to outcomes writing is the most difficult with 60% whereas each of listening and speaking has 20%.

After carrying out some analyses and discussion on pieces of information collected with one of the methods used in data collection, let us attack the next sub-section which is concerned with the Analysis and Discussion of Results from Students Questionnaire.

6.2 Analysis and Discussion of Results from Students' Questionnaire

We began by setting the first question which was posed to the students to know the grade in which they started learning English, this question is important for the teacher to have such knowledge so that they can figure out in which level the students might be concerned to English language. According to the outcomes most of them started learning English in the grade 7, (55%), whereas grade 8 is the second with 14%, and grade 9 is the third with 12%. In the next position comes grade 6 and 5 with 9% and 6% for grade 5, the last one is grade 10 with 4%.

The second question was addressed to EFL students to know about their extra-training after schooling. It is very crucial having extra activities regarding ELT during their extra-classes, so that they can engage their selves on developing their gaps in every skill. But unfortunately, in this class only 12 students have extra-training after normal school, the rest 54 students have never had this opportunity; as a results, most of them still stragglng on writing a well-structured paragraph.

The results of the third question as they are presented in the diagram 4 help us to know in reality which language aspect students face more difficult. As a matter of fact, 11th grade students from Teacher training course Magistério BG 4011-Cubal are still uncooked on writing with 30%, while speaking is the second with 21%, next comes listening with 15%, in the fourth position comes reading with 11%, finally comes the two less difficult aspects which are vocabulary with 6% and grammar with 5%.

7 Text analyses

Illustration 1: After reading carefully this paragraph, we have noticed that the student respects some rules of writing an effective paragraph, such as cohesion, unity, coherence and paragraph organization.

Cohesion- the entire paragraph is co-textually well connected because there are some linking words showing the relationship between the ideas in other clauses: and, also, in fact ...; the grammar structure rule is well used. For instance, in sentence 'I didn't come because I drank something bad and I had to see a nurse';

Unity- the paragraph is effectively unified because each sentence shows consistence on a single idea, no one gets strayed from the main point. For example, from the begging, 'I'm very sorry for.... To the end', 'I'll make sure I do it';

Coherence- there is internal logic through paragraph. That is there is clarity in nouns and pronouns; the used language is descriptive and precise, that is to say, we have the topic sentence, the supporting sentences and the concluding sentence designed correctly.

And the last logical writing strategies well used in this paragraph is **paragraph organization:**

The topic sentence: «I'm very sorry for not coming to school yesterday». This topic sentence is correctly designed and it presents in short what the text is about.

The supporting sentences: The supporting sentences start from «I didn't come because.... Up to school again». They really provide the details which support the topic sentence; and

The concluding sentence: «Please give me any work I missed yesterday. I'll make sure I do it». In short, this concluding sentence retails the reality in the topic sentence in concluding the idea.

From all accounts, this student seems to have a little writing intelligence because he could go through with four demanding good paragraph writing strategies. Concerning format, he has a good handwriting and what misses is only the skill of using well the page margins. This paragraph, despite the fact that the position of the sheet of paper does not enable us to analyze correctly the placement of the content on four margins of the page (left, right, top, bottom margin), at least, the left and the right margins should have left a little bit from each margin. And the title itself should be centered.

Illustration 2: After reading carefully this text, we have noticed that some aspects regarding writing a correct paragraph are missing, and some other aspects are wrongly used. First of all, the paragraph organization is not correctly designed. There are a huge lack of coherence and cohesion; moreover, the text presents many grammatical mistakes. The placement of the text on the sheet does not respect any rules because we do not have any marginal spaces either on the right side of the sheet of paper or on the left side. The student was even unable to write the lines rightly. In conclusion ; this paragraph is totally incorrect. There are no margins and space are really short.

8 Analysis and Discussion of Results from Classroom Observation Chart

This section, like previous one (text analyses), offers qualitative data collected in the field by the time teachers were delivering their lessons. We analyzed many aspects during classroom observation but among them we have selected some frequent writing activities and strategies.

Since this research paper is based on paragraph writing strategies and techniques and question answer technique, we closely observed the most teaching techniques used by the teachers. Unfortunately, none of them has ever used the above-mentioned techniques to teach writing skills. From close classroom observations we assessed different teaching components which we brought them down here for deep analysis and discussion.

We have observed carefully the five teachers when delivering their sessions. From our close observation, we have noticed that teachers, most of them, lack strategies to conduct effectively a lesson that has to do with writing activity.

We have conducted a close classroom observation where we followed every EFL teacher while delivering one of their sessions of grade 11 classrooms selected. Every observation allowed us to notice that teachers still struggle to teach well how to write a good paragraph. The relevant fact that we could observe is that most of the participants failed in using some effective strategies through writing. Most of the lessons observed were focused principally on speaking, reading and some grammar. Unfortunately, the five teachers have never taught the specific strategies and techniques related to a correct paragraph. In here we could see that most of teachers seem to have difficulties to set clearly their teaching goals and problem.

So far, we strongly feel relieved due to this article we went through. In short, we could mention the background statement of the work, some authors theoretical assumptions, the tools such as teacher questionnaire, student questionnaire text analyses and classroom observation chart that we used in the research to collect the data. We hope that by having gone through these all issues, we are already almost at the end of our activity, so the next sections missing is - Conclusions.

9 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The current article has examined some effective teaching writing strategies or techniques used in paragraph writing activities to raise ELT teachers' awareness of the use of effective strategies to write a good paragraph.

The study has thought for the reasons of the existence of certain numbers of rules which have to be followed while writing a standard paragraph. Being writing regarded as a the most difficult activity skill comparing to other skills such as, speaking, listening and reading, it dawned on the researcher to go a fairly deeper on this theme because ELT learners in general, and grade 11 of "Magistério BG 4011 in Cubal" particularly, cannot understand the principles of a good paragraph writing.

Owing to lack of principles to understand well how to write an effective paragraph, this work had to use some scholars' theoretical issues related to the two key words such as, **writing** and **paragraph**.

On seeking for reasons of the origin of certain numbers of rules which have to be followed while writing a standard paragraph, the current work analysed the problematic of composition of a good paragraph writing relating to some **logical strategies in a paragraph** such as, coherence; cohesion and unity; paragraph organization and format. The study has come to the conclusion that EFL teachers should be more creative in using some techniques and strategies to enhance the ELT learners to write a well-structured paragraph. Also the learners' participations in some writing tuition with a professional and in workshop or seminar concerning types of writing such as, personal, public, creative, social, academic and institutional is essential for learning well how a good paragraph is built.

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